

BADIIY ASARDA LEKSIK VOSITALAR O'RNI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada yozuvchi-shoirlar, ijodkor badiiy asar yaratishda asar ta'sirchanlik kuchini oshirishda, emotsional-ekspressiv ifodani yanada go'zal qilib ifodalashda asosiy vosita hisoblangan shakldosh, ma'nodosh, zid ma'noli, ko'p ma'noli, tarixiy-arxaik va shunga o'xshash bir qator leksik birliklardan foydalanish haqida fikr yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar. Ma'nodosh so'zlar, zid ma'noli, ko'p ma'noli, tarixiy-arxaik so'zlar, badiiy asar, yozuvchi, shoir.

Annotation. The article discusses about the lexical units of the language which helps writers and poets, using synonymous words, opposite meaning, polysemantic words, historical-archaic words, when creating a literary work. These lexical items are the main tool for increasing the effectiveness of the work, expressing the emotional-expressive expression in a beautiful way.

Key words. Synonymous words, opposite meaning, polysemantic words, historical-archaic words, literary work, writer, poet.

Аннотация. В статье говорится о лексических единицах языка, которые помогают писателям и поэтам, используя слова-синонимы, противоположные по значению, многозначные слова, историко-архаичные слова, при создании литературного произведения. Эти лексические единицы являются основным средством повышения эффективности работы, красиво выражая эмоционально-экспрессивное выражение.

Ключевые слова. Синонимичные слова, противоположное значение, многозначные слова, историко-архаические слова, литературное произведение, писатель, поэт.

In the process of linguistic analysis of the literary text, it is required to identify the lexical units that show the writer's skill in using the language, the emotional-expressive expressions are realized in a bubble, and to reflect on the extent to which they served the artistic-aesthetic purpose of the writer. For this purpose, synonyms, synonyms, antonyms, polysemantic words, historical and archaic words, new creations, dialectal words, foreign and vulgar words in the language

of the literary work are distinguished and what is relevant to the work it is explained that it was imported with a purpose¹.

Language is not only a means of oral communication between people, but also the main tool of fiction. Because writers and poets skilfully create a literary image through the medium of language. There are forms of language such as literary language and poetic language. The writers and poets use words, which are the main lexical units of the language, to describe various natural scenes, human feelings, experiences, fiction works. They use it to describe events vividly and impressively.

As you can see, the linguistic units of the language not only ensure speech activity between people, but also play an important role in the creation of literary works that serve to enrich the human spiritual world. It is for this reason that the lexical-semantic layer of the language has become the object of research in several areas of linguistics.

The lexical-semantic organization of the text structure has been under close scrutiny in numerous philological approaches: text linguistics (Halliday and Hasan, 1976), lexical semantics (Geeraerts, 2009; Jeffries, 2014; Mills, 2005), communicative linguistics (Gee, 2010a; 2010b), literary stylistics (Hope and Wright, 2005; Shen, 2014; Toolan, 2013), pragmatic stylistics (Black, 2006; Warner, 2014)².

It depends on the skill of the writer and poet that the words, phrases and expressions are used masterfully and in their place, and that the content of the work is fully conveyed to the reader. The writer effectively uses the special lexical possibilities of the language (synonyms and antonyms, archaisms and neologisms, dialectism and jargonism, professionalism and barbarism), as well as monologues, dialogues, and polylogues. The features and theoretical foundations of the language of the work of art are covered in scientific literature³.

In addition, literary works are welcomed by the reader with great interest, the perfect description of the content of the work, descriptive and expressive means of the language (simile, metaphor, revitalization), poetic figures (rhetorical questioning, appeal and appeal, reinforcement of repetition, parallelism,

¹ Text of lectures on "Linguistic analysis of artistic text". (2012). Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyaz.

² Shainer, Iryna & Bekhta, Ivan & Karp, Marta & Tatarovska, Olesya & Kovalevska, Tetiana. (2022). Lexical combinations of contemporary British military fiction: lexical-semantic and stylistic features. Revista Amazonia Investiga. 11. 29-39. 10.34069/AI/2022.55.07.3.

³ Кожевникова Н.А. Избранные работы по языку художественной литературы. - М.2011

juxtaposition, inversion, etc.) and the use of poetic arts (tazad, talmeh, istiora) are also important in increasing the effectiveness of an literary work.

J. P. Gee (2010a, p. 67) that no matter which part of the context influenced our interpretation of the text, “there is always the possibility of considering other and additional aspects of the context, and these new considerations may change how we interpret the utterance”.

As mentioned above, the effective use of synonyms, antonyms, polysemantic words, historical and archaic words, new creations, and dialectal words in the creation of an literary work increases the colourfulness of the language of the work.

In conclusion, it should be said that the use of various units of the literary language layer by creative writers and poets in the text of an literary work not only increases the emotional-expressive power of the work, the expressiveness of artistic speech, but also shows the ability of the creator to use language. In a word, the use of these language units is the main factor that shows the expressiveness and effectiveness of the work, the lexical richness of the language.

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